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Staying or Leaving Academia? Career Development of VET Doctoral Researchers in Times of Uncertainty

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Abstract

Context: In recent years, there has been an increasing focus on the promotion of emerging researchers. Due to the growing number of PhD students and the decrease in post-doctoral positions, the preparation of PhD students for careers outside academia has become more and more important. This study addresses the career aspirations of doctoral researchers in the field of vocational education and training, considering the pandemic-related influences on their career development and the support offered within the doctoral programme.

Approach: Six doctoral researchers from three different European countries (Germany, England, Sweden) were interviewed online in semi-structured interviews. The countries were chosen because of their different VET systems. In addition, the interview partners conduct their doctorate under different organizational conditions: structured programmes vs. individual doctoral education. The data was analysed using the method of focused analysis of qualitative interviews.

Findings: Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the framework conditions of the doctorate have changed, and many challenges have arisen for doctoral researchers, independent of the structure of the doctoral programme or the VET system. Nevertheless, the structured doctoral programme in Sweden, a country with a science-oriented VET system, tends to prepare students more strongly for a career within academia than the doctoral programmes in the other countries. With regard to the career aspirations of the doctoral students surveyed, on the other hand, a strong tendency toward career aspirations outside academia can be observed.

Conclusion: The pandemic-related circumstances have not allowed the doctoral researchers to network within the scientific community and beyond as they had hoped. The result - regardless of the doctoral programme or country - is that the interviewees are facing an uncertain future with regard to the end of their doctorate.

Keywords: doctoral education, career development, career aspirations, PhD students, vocational education and training

1 Problem Statement

The times when doctorates served the primary goal of professorships or tenure-track positions are long gone. The number of doctoral researchers far exceeds the number of academic positions available (Fuhrmann et al., 2011; Konsortium Bundesbericht Wissenschaftlicher Nachwuchs, 2021; Seo et al., 2021). Recent studies have concluded that careers outside academia can no longer be described as alternative career paths but have become the predominant career path for young academics (Fuhrmann et al., 2011; St. Clair et al., 2017). Furthermore, as doctoral researchers increasingly pursue careers outside academia, preparation for both academic

career opportunities as well as non-academic career paths is becoming more important (European University Association, 2019; Konsortium Bundesbericht Wissenschaftlicher Nachwuchs, 2021).

In Europe, doctoral education has undergone major changes in recent years. In 2011, the European Commission developed "The European Framework for Research Careers", which divides researchers into four broad profiles – including necessary and desirable characteristics – that are independent of country, profession, private or public sector (European Commission, 2011):

- R1 First Stage Researcher (up to the point of PhD)
- R2 Recognised Researcher (PhD holders or equivalent who are not yet fully independent)
- R3 Established Researcher (researchers who have developed a level of independence.)
- R4 Leading Researcher (researchers leading their research area or field)

In this study, the terms "first stage researcher", "PhD student", "doctoral student" and "doctoral researcher" are used synonymously.

Results of a study by the Council for Doctoral Education of the European University Association (EUA, 2019) show that doctoral education nowadays predominantly takes place in structured programmes or schools rather than as individual education only. The EUA study concludes that universities in Europe offer support opportunities that pursue both academic and non-academic career paths and that while doctoral researchers are mainly seen as future academics, they are also increasingly seen as tomorrow's professionals.

2 Theoretical Frame and Research Questions

In order to understand doctoral researchers' career decision making, Seo et al. (2021) used the social cognitive career theory (SCCT)'s model of career self-management (CSM) by Lent and Brown (2013). They found out that advice from faculty members has a significant impact on the desire to pursue a career inside academia or to stay in the faculty and that doctoral researchers in the field of social sciences are more likely to stay in academia than those of science and engineering.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, there have been unpredictable changes in private and professional lives worldwide. The circumstances of this uncertain time - such as the closure of facilities, contact and travel restrictions - make it difficult for all academics to conduct their research. Social distancing measures reduce face-to-face meetings and network interactions. Consequently, collaboration and the natural exchange of ideas through informal conversations are limited (Termini & Traver, 2020). Therefore, this study also examines the influence of the current Corona situation on the career development of first stage researchers in Europe, considering different organisational types of doctoral education: individual education vs. structured programmes/schools (European University Association, 2007, 2019).

This study aims to analyse the career development of doctoral researchers in the field of vocational education and training (VET). VET has been chosen as field of research because the study is embedded in a work package on promoting emerging researchers as part of the scientific *Meta-Project on Research for the Internationalization of Vocational Training* (MP-IN-VET), funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF). In order to gain new insights that can be used in this networking effort, the participants in this study are primarily not from the funding line, have been contacted randomly and come from countries beyond the project, which will be explained in the following chapter.

The research questions are:

- (1) What differences in the professional development of doctoral researchers result from the different types of doctoral training or the VET systems of the countries?

- (2) To what extent do the Corona-related circumstances impact the career development of VET doctoral researchers?
- (3) How well do VET doctoral researchers feel prepared for a career inside and outside academia?
- (4) Are they more likely to pursue a career inside or outside academia?

3 Methodology

Previous studies have mainly focused on the natural and engineering sciences (Seo et al., 2021; St. Clair et al., 2017). What these studies also do not focus on are the COVID-19-related challenges and opportunities that influence the career development of doctoral researchers at the current time.

In order to gain a deeper insight into the topic, a qualitative research approach is applied. To answer the research questions, semi-structured interviews were conducted from March to June 2022 with six first stage researchers (R1) in vocational education and training who are currently in the data collection/analysis or "all-but-dissertation" stage. The interviewees complete their doctorate in three different European countries (Germany, Sweden, United Kingdom (UK)). Per country, two interviews were conducted with doctoral researchers from different universities. These three countries were selected because of their different VET models. They can be classified according to Greinert's (2004) typology as follows: market orientation (UK), science orientation (Sweden), vocational orientation (Germany). Since these forms are historically determined, there is an assumption that these traditions may also have an influence on the formation of PhD programmes. In addition, the three countries offer different organizational conditions for the doctorate in vocational education and training:

- Germany (individual doctoral education, no compulsory studies, financed by temporary project employment, teaching obligations may be contractually regulated)
- Sweden (structured PhD programme in education, obligatory course work, paid positions as employee/PhD student, 20 % of the working time may be spent for work within the department, e.g. for teaching)
- UK (both individual and structured doctoral education, high tuition fees to cover study costs, obligatory course work only in the structured programme)

The interviews were conducted online via Zoom, recorded with OBS, and transcribed verbatim. Categories were developed from the interview guideline (see table 2) and were used to code all interviews. It has to be noted here that this article represents only one aspect of the entire study. In addition to the career development and career aspirations of the doctoral researchers, other aspects of professional development (such as participation in trainings, informal learning, networking, internationalisation) and the structure of the different doctoral programmes (such as financing, supervision, publishing, teaching and study obligation) with their perceived advantages and disadvantages were also surveyed.

Table 2
Information on the Interviewees

Acro- nym	Gen- der	Country & Ed. Type	Educational Background	PhD Motivation
GER1	Female	Germany (individual, full-time)	Apprenticeship as industrial clerk, work and travel experience, several years tour guide abroad, employee at agency for language travels, studies in business education	Never intended to do a doctorate, was asked by supervisor, hopes the title will open doors for her
GER2	Male	Germany (individual, full-time)	Apprenticeship as electronics technician for industrial engineering, studies in electrical engineering and working as a tutor, then Master's degree for teaching at vocational schools	Interested in the content, asked the supervisor for a job, the title has no significance for him
SWE1	Female	Sweden (structured, full-time)	Bachelor's degree in primary school teaching, Master's degree in international and comparative education, internships at international organisations abroad	Wanted to do a PhD since she was 17, wants to find answers and a stable salary for four years, applied for the programme
SWE2	Male	Sweden (structured, full-time)	Apprenticeship as electrician, teacher in philosophy and history for upper-secondary education, incl. being a "first teacher" (train instructors how to teach)	Wants to understand people, does not care about the title, applied for the programme
UK1	Female	England (individual, full-time)	Teacher (vice principle) in a non-European country, Master's degree with focus on technical vocational education and training	Got scholarship to continue her master's studies; wants to contribute her quotes in the world and use the title to her advantage
UK2	Female	England (structured, part-time)	Studied communication and media, worked abroad as English language teacher, then did teacher qualification and Master's degree in education policy and society, currently part-time employed as teacher at a vocational school	Supervisor of the Master thesis encouraged her to do a PhD, then she applied as she wants to understand certain problems and to find solutions for practice

Of the six interviews, two were conducted in German (GER1, GER2) and the other four in English (SWE1, SWE2, UK1, UK2). The data was coded with MAXQDA software and analysed using the method of focused analysis of qualitative interviews according to Kuckartz and Rädiker (2020), in which text segments from all interviewees are compiled on a specific topic and thus can be processed into a summarizing text.

Table 3
Categories and Sub-Categories of the Study

	Category PhD	Corona	Career Development
Sub-Categories	- Background Information	- Impact on Doctoral Project	- Preparation through university
	- Motivation	- Impact on Professional Development	- Individual feeling of being prepared
	- Added Value/Advantages	- Impact on Career Development	- Career aspiration outside academia
	- Disadvantages	- General Challenges	- Career aspiration inside academia
		- Chances	- Other influencing factors or findings
		- Other influencing factors or findings	

4 Findings

The presentation of the findings is structured according to the individual research questions, starting with an analysis of the differences between the different types of doctoral education and the VET systems.

4.1 Differences between Types of Doctoral Education and the VET Systems

In order to address the question of possible differences in the preparation of doctoral researchers for a post-doctoral career through their universities, it should be mentioned that the interviewees come from countries with different VET systems according to Greinert (2004) and that they do their doctorates in programmes with different degrees of structure (see table 3).

Table 4

Overview of Interviewees by VET System and Structure of the Doctorate

Country	VET Model	Interviewee	Type of Doct. Ed.	Status	Study Obligation
Germany	Vocational orientation	GER1	Individual	Full-time Employee & PhD Student	None
		GER2	Individual	Full-time Employee & PhD Student	None
Sweden	Science orientation	SWE1	Structured	Full-time Employee & PhD Student	90 ECTS
		SWE2	Structured	Full-time Employee & PhD Student	90 ECTS
United Kingdom (England)	Market orientation	UK1	Individual	PhD Student (scholarship for study fees only)	None
		UK2	Structured	Part-time teacher & Part-time PhD Student (studentship covers a stipend and study fees)	Compulsory induction week

First of all, it should be noted that doctoral researchers in Germany and Sweden finance their doctorates through an employment contract as research associates. In England, on the other hand, the interviewees have a status as PhD students only and have to pay high tuition fees, which in the case of UK1 and UK2 are covered by scholarships. While UK2 is doing a doctorate in a structured programme and also receives financial support for living expenses, UK1 has to pay for her own living expenses within the framework of the individual doctorate. With regard to the financing of the doctorate, clear differences can be seen between the different VET systems:

- Self-financed or via scholarships in England (market orientation) vs.
- Employee status in Germany and Sweden (Vocational & Science Orientation).

With regard to the professional development of doctoral researchers through the university, it should be noted that the structured programme in Sweden provides the strongest institutionalised support for the (academic) training of doctoral researchers. This is evidenced by this statement from SWE2:

It's more of an apprenticeship programme than when I became an electrician. ... they have apprenticeship written in the curriculum because very much of the development as a PhD is, according to my experience, is very much on text. I write a text, I send it to my supervisors, we have a meeting about it, and they give me comments. I take these comments, and I do and re-do and work, and battle anxiety and all the things that come with the writing process and I see that I develop as a writer, but it's, that is the main

focus, it's about writing texts and getting comments, texts, and working to become published, how to become published, what do you do, how do you think.

In addition to the mandatory 90 ECTS credits, this strong focus on publishing reflects the science orientation of the Swedish VET system. The regular submission of literature reviews also plays an important role in the structured doctorate of interviewee UK2, but for the purpose of developing the doctoral topic and less against the background of publication. Unlike the Swedish doctoral researchers, where the focus is on publishing, and both interview partners do cumulative doctorates, only the best dissertations (monographies) are published at UK1's department (see Vocational Education System England: Market Orientation). UK2 is also writing a 100,000 word dissertation. However, at the time of the interview, she did not know whether her dissertation will or must be published. The two German doctoral researchers are also writing a monography. Due to the embedding or financing of the doctorate through third-party funding, their current publications have a strong project reference and are less related to the dissertation. Beyond that, there is no obligation to study. However, UK1, as well as GER1 and GER2 from the individual programmes and UK2 from the structured programme (only with a compulsory introductory week that introduces empirical work), have the opportunity to participate by interest in a comprehensive pool of seminars offered by their university.

4.2 Impact of the Pandemic

The pandemic-related restrictions and changes in work life and society have influenced different aspects of the interviewees' doctoral projects as well as their professional development. From the interview data, the answers could be allocated based on the following categories: Accessibility, travel restriction, networking, research design, digitisation, informal get-together, geo-political situation, individual and health problems.

With regard to *accessibility*, it was mentioned that the doctoral project could only be registered with a delay because the university was temporarily closed and inaccessible (GER1). It was also no longer possible to reach or visit vocational schools in the home country and abroad (GER1, GER2, SWE2). Instead of experiencing school practice, SWE2, therefore, devoted more time to literature. It was also described as difficult to carry out acquisitions of new contacts/interview partners and meetings without a local presence (GER1, SWE2); many emails or calls remained unanswered (GER1).

Actually, I would have liked to go to schools much more and learn in a way that I could really look at school practice, talk to the teachers etc. ... None of that was possible. (GER2, translated by the author)

The issue of *travel restrictions* in particular meant that field access was uncertain for GER1 and there were difficulties with the time difference. In the case of GER2, the project partners could not be invited to a meeting to get to know each other and to start the project as planned. In addition, there were no travels abroad for data collection (GER1) or as a possible study visit abroad (SWE1, SWE2).

So, it was never part of my plan to travel for data collection. I wanted to focus the study on Sweden. But what I wanted to do and then still find to do, is like I wanted to have a study visiting a university abroad, mostly for networking purposes. (SWE1)

The lack of *networking* opportunities was mentioned several times (GER1, SWE1, SWE2). In addition, it was regretted that (international) conference participation in presence was not possible (GER1, SWE1, UK1, UK2):

I have only attended virtual events so far, so I imagine it would have been different and run differently in presence and I'm sure there would have been good networking, but that has not been my experience, to be honest. (GER1, translated by the author)

But career-wise I think it's hurting me, because I don't have the networking, I don't have the teaching in person, which means that I will apply for a job that I have never tried before. In the future if I want to become a lecturer. And then, of course, like any types of connection with the industry are not there. I think it hasn't been very helpful in our case. And interviewing is hard, collecting data is hard, people have been busy with moving online and back in the classroom and back online, so they were not that much available. I see a lot of negatives into that. I am sorry. (SWE1)

Due to the difficult accessibility and lack of travel opportunities, five of the six doctoral researchers interviewed had to adapt their *research design*. For example, the research methods had to be rescheduled or adapted to the pandemic-related contact restrictions (GER1, GER2, SWE1), as they were no longer possible in person and could not be conducted online; for example a method similar to family constellation (GER2). In addition, two doctoral researchers struggled with a very low response rate or high drop-outs (GER1, SWE2). Because of the adjustments to the research design and the difficulty in reaching contact persons, half of the interviewees experienced time constraints in their doctoral project, which were partially compensated for by extending third-party funding or scholarships (GER1, SWE1, UK1).

I think the main thing is one of the groups was very hard to get hold of through telephone, so I missed the opportunity to go to the school to say: "Hey, you promised me an interview." (SWE2)

The pandemic-related *digitisation* caused some challenges from the respondents' point of view with regard to conducting online interviews. GER1 mentioned the poorer quality of interviews due to connection problems, and SWE2 struggles with interview recordings in different file formats due to a mixture of smartphone and videoconferencing programmes that have to be played through different audio players. UK2 stated that all social events, as well as seminar groups and trainings, take place online. The trainings are also mostly self-study videos, and when online trainings with participants take place, many of them turn off their cameras:

The social aspect is completely missing, which feels like isolation. (UK2)

It is precisely this social aspect, the loss of *informal get-togethers*, that has the greatest negative impact on the professional development of the doctoral students surveyed. Due to the pandemic, not only were there no informal conversations with participants in their PhD projects (GER2), but there were also fewer people on campus and in the offices during and after the pandemic (SWE2, UK1, UK2). Working in a home office also took away the possibility of informal corridor talks, which are perceived as very valuable (GER1, SWE1, SWE2).

At our institute yes, we rather stay at home and just sometimes meet at the university. ... just grab a coffee, talk to someone, that really enriches your professional life and

everything and that is something which we, at the moment, don't have. In the last year, I worked at the university just one day, which is maybe a little bit my fault, but you will not really meet people there. It's a very sad situation. The feeling of a community within the department was kind of lost during the pandemic. (SWE2)

But the informal aspects are also very very useful and fun and it gives, I think it gives a lot more depth to the education. Also, like grabbing a cup of coffee is in some way arena for learning also because if someone else took a cup of coffee I can ask them about things. Or as others ask me about things also. (SWE1)

In addition to the previously mentioned negative factors of the pandemic on the doctoral researchers' PhD projects, other aspects were mentioned that are summarised here. For example, the *geo-political situation in Eastern Europe* was mentioned (GER1, UK1) and the uncertainty as to what impact this could have on career opportunities. Other complaints were that due to the pandemic, teaching experience in person was not possible, a network for job applications was lacking (SWE1) and information events for the time after the doctorate were not held (UK1). Moreover, one interviewee also complained about *health problems* due to the work in the home office:

I didn't have a proper office, and I didn't have a proper desk or chair or anything. I had a lot of, like, physical pain like from sitting in the wrong chair with the wrong table. Psychological it was like crazy like I was working here, and I was cooking here. And that is not productive, of course. And that has been a really hard time for me. (SWE1)

In addition, there were further *individual problems* that hindered progress in the meantime: mental reasons (UK1), psyche/depression (GER2, SWE1, SWE2, UK1), lack of motivation/work ethic (SWE2), and the feeling of isolation/lack of human interaction (GER2, SWE1, SWE2, UK1, UK2).

It was all my friends in the PhD, everyone had to take extensions, it was a demoralising wee challenging time. ... You know, it was from sad news every day, it was from family members getting sick, it was the whole isolation and depression that came with it. Not being able to meet colleagues, not even to hear from people, Zoom calls were people getting fatigued. You know, Zoom calls, it was mentally too much. It was the fear, you know, that the new media projected; it was everything. So that thing cut off PhD life, to be honest. (UK1)

Besides all the negative points mentioned before, *positive aspects* that the pandemic has brought were also listed, especially in the area of digitisation: the "Zoom culture" has become normal and has opened up new communication opportunities (UK2), doctoral researchers and colleagues are used to digital video and collaboration tools (SWE2), video conferencing systems allow to attend a meeting or conference and do something else at the same time (SWE1), and tools for asynchronous work, e.g. Miro, continue to be used after the pandemic (GER2). In addition, GER2 mentioned that accessibility is generally better, and GER1 found it easier to reach people from other universities. SWE1 and SWE2 both reflected on their teaching methods.

If you would walk around here, you would never think there has been a pandemic, you would never think there is still Corona, but in our teaching, we have, we still

use some digital aspects that are left in because, yeah, these are good. And also meetings with other people can be done through Zoom without having to; it's easy to have digital meetings now. For better and for worse. (SWE2)

With regard to the pandemic situation, it can be concluded that there are no significant differences between the countries or doctoral programmes - basically, all interview partners have to deal with the same challenges. Only in Sweden there was no hard lockdown as in Germany and England, but the urgent recommendation to work from the home office:

For us, there was not many restrictions in society at all. I think the restriction that people, in general, most complained about was that restaurants had to close at ten. That is what people complained about. And at the university, there was a policy of work at home when you can. Classes were mostly through Zoom or other types of, yeah, like Microsoft Teams, but some people were at the office; I was here, for example, I have a hard time working at home. (SWE2)

4.3 University Preparation for Careers Inside and Outside Academia

Events organised by the university on post-doctoral career paths are compulsory in the structured programmes (SWE1, SWE2, UK2), while in the individual doctorate (GER1, GER2, UK1) participation in such an event is based on personal initiative, whereby GER1 was unsure whether such an offer even existed at all at her university. UK1 attended a programme called "What to do with a PhD?", which was offered by the university, and which was very helpful for her personally. However, she criticises that it is easy to miss such events for the following reason:

I mean, university has this career newsletter, career experts, ... An email is just sent, and if you miss the email, you miss it. ... in the end I feel that we have a lot of value in terms of professional development going on. But you tend just to not know, if you miss the email. (UK1)

In the structured doctoral programmes of the respondents from Sweden and England, an information session on career opportunities after the doctorate takes place as part of the introduction to PhD studies. From the point of view of UK2, the timing within the "induction programme" was too early and there was too much information at once within one week. Also in Sweden, the information on career opportunities after the doctorate takes place at the beginning of the doctorate:

When I started the first years, we go through this obligatory programme that is called introduction to PhD-programme, to PhD studies. And in that block of seminars, there was one discussion about how academia is structured and how are different positions within academy and how one moves from a PhD-student like graduate to get in a lecturer position and so on. So, that was like an overview there. ... But we have this introduction once. So, this is something we talked about; yes, then we have the seminars that happen on the university level. That are about funding and post-docs. This is like research outside of academia or after PhD that the information is always on this university general level. No one has ever talked about industry opportunities and stuff, that is a no. I guess it might happen on a personal level like I meet you and you meet me, and you say: "SWE1, there is this option", but nothing like organised from the department. (SWE1)

In the structured programmes, these events, which are organised at the university level, on the one hand, take place at a time when this content is not the focus of doctoral researchers, and on the other hand, they mainly focus on a career within academia.

Within the scope of *supervision*, the three interviewees from structured programmes reported that they had informal discussions with their supervisors, but the ideas were mostly within academia. The second supervisor from UK2 suggested a post-doc that not necessarily has to be very academic but where the results of the PhD can be applied in another context. To conclude, she feels that she learns “how to fit in that group” and she has the feeling that “academia is far removed from practice”, which makes her worry about whether her PhD studies have an influence on her so that she will behave differently than before. While GER1 had an informal conversation about her career development, UK1 stated that no one has ever questioned her what her career aspiration after the PhD is. For GER2 this is the complete opposite. In annual meetings, the long-term perspective is addressed, and there is also a lot of informal discussion with the supervisor about the future after the PhD. The supervisor puts a lot of thought into this and also takes the doctoral researcher to meetings regarding his next career step by establishing contacts that could be helpful later on.

It is evident from the interview data that in the university context, the preparation of doctoral researchers for post-doctoral career opportunities has a strong focus on an academic career:

Oh, it's lacking here; this is something the university as whole lacks in, because we are very much in a development process for being inside the university, not much outside university. (SWE2)

As a result, the many career opportunities outside academia remain unknown:

I am very curious on what opportunities I do have outside, so, I have been asking and pushing, but I think people might actually not know that, at the end of the day. I am not sure, but I still have not figured out what are the opportunities outside academia. (SWE1)

Thus, it depends on the individual supervisor whether and to what extent career paths outside academia are identified. In addition, it can be noted that the doctoral researchers face an uncertain professional future:

Also, a problem is that everyone who works here wants us to keep working here, so there is a will to keep us here. But to keep us here, there must be any money. ... and these things can be sensitive, so we don't talk about it. (SWE2)

4.4 Staying or Leaving Academia?

After talking about the differences between individual and structured doctorates, the impact of the pandemic on the doctoral project and career development, as well as the university preparation for careers inside and outside academia, the final research question will be answered in this section: Are VET doctoral researchers more likely to pursue a career inside or outside academia?

Of the six interviewees, only SWE2 pursues a career inside academia:

The hope is getting a post-doc or other type of teaching position, but it's, yeah, it's a gloom horizon. ... my hope, my end goal is somewhen becoming a lecturer doing more teaching than I do now and therefore less research, but I want to still be able to continue my research project and do new stuff, and I also like teaching. So, but if I, but

becoming a lecturer is hard, so my hopes are, lie in a post-doc for a year or two after. And if I don't, if I am not able to get a post-doc then maybe try another university or go back to teaching.

For him, a career outside academia, such as going back to teaching, is only his plan B. On the contrary, SWE1 pursues an academic career only as the second (teaching) and third (post-doc) option. She is more interested in the change that research can bring. From her perspective, university research brings change, but not with the same impact as she can see outside academia. That is why she would like to do research connected to policy. Ideally, that would mean to her to be employed at the Ministry of Education, working on curricular programmes or teacher training, and also doing research. However, as SWE1 is not convinced of having a chance to get such a position at the ministry level, she would also be open to other opportunities:

I would prefer to work with something that has a research part. A part of my work to be research-connected, and the other part can be teaching, can be administration, project management, but I want a part that is research.

Even though UK2's second supervisor suggested a post-doc position after the doctorate in order to apply the results of her dissertation in another context, her career aspirations are currently not focused on this idea. She can imagine self-employment as a consultant for colleges, working with the management team to build structures, and at the same time continuing her teaching job. GER1 would like to work in the field of project management in international projects. GER2 is not aiming for an academic career either. He can well imagine working for a social partner, in the public service or in an affiliated institution. In addition, like UK2, he could imagine being self-employed in the future. UK1 would also like to find a position outside academia, as she realised

... that academia will not be fulfilling for me. It will be boring as a matter of fact for my kind of person. ... I like to make changes. I don't say academia does not give you the opportunity to make changes, but industry gives me more opportunities. So, I am going into talent development and management.

Finally, a few general aspects can be observed. For example, GER1 is uncertain because she has no idea how good her career opportunities are due to the pandemic and geopolitical situation. In addition, the two doctoral students from Germany mentioned the desire for planning security and a permanent employment contract. GER2 would like to be able to take out a loan after completing his doctorate. This is something that a job at the university cannot currently offer him. For SWE2, the uncertainty of not knowing what will happen to him after his doctorate is very stressful.

So that, those PhDs that are at the end of their PhD programme like myself and others in my cohort, there is some kind of growing anxiety of what is supposed to happen after. And we are a bit overcrowded in this department. So, we know that when the four of us are done, then maybe doesn't exist any work for us here or if it does, there is room for one of us, and that's very sad because we have been not living together, but developing together, in four years now. And even if someone gets to stay, it wouldn't be the same because the other three are gone. Or something happens and everybody gets to stay; we don't know. And the unknown part is not good. (SWE2)

In summary, it can be noted that only one of the six doctoral researchers interviewed is aiming for a career in academia; all the others would like to pursue a non-academic career path.

5 Discussion

The doctorate during and after the pandemic is not comparable to the time before Corona, and the geopolitical situation also plays a role in personal well-being and career prospects for some interviewees. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the framework conditions of the doctorate have changed, and many challenges have arisen for doctoral researchers. To summarize, the following factors can be stated to have a negative influence on the doctoral project: reduced face-to-face meetings and network interactions, the decline in informal feedback, limited field access, adaptation of research methods, delay in completion of the dissertation (Konsortium Bundesbericht Wissenschaftlicher Nachwuchs, 2021; Termini & Traver, 2020). In addition, seminars and further education courses are conducted predominantly online (Autor:innen-gruppe Bildungsberichtserstattung, 2022). On the other hand, also positive aspects were highlighted: improvement of digital competencies, an increased virtual international collaboration (Konsortium Bundesbericht Wissenschaftlicher Nachwuchs, 2021; Termini & Traver, 2020; Wößmann et al., 2021), and some tools for collaborations have been integrated into post-pandemic teaching.

The observations from the field of social sciences that doctoral researchers often pursue an academic career (Seo et al., 2021) cannot be confirmed on the basis of the interviews conducted with doctoral researchers from the field of VET. Careers outside academia have become their predominant career path (Fuhrmann et al., 2011; St. Clair et al., 2017), which underlines the importance of preparing doctoral researchers also for non-academic career paths (European University Association, 2019; Konsortium Bundesbericht Wissenschaftlicher Nachwuchs, 2021).

Although the results of the presented study confirm the tendency that universities prepare students for an academic career (career development support as an integral part of structured programmes, EUA, 2019), five out of six interview partners prefer a career outside academia. It is not surprising that the one person with career aspirations within academia comes from a structured programme with a science-oriented VET system (Sweden). In the case of the individual doctorate in Germany (VET model: vocational orientation), it is more a matter of the relationship between doctoral researcher and supervisor, comparable to the relationship between apprentice and training instructor in a dual approach, who takes the apprentice by the hand. The degree of guidance and support depends strongly on the individual personality of the supervisor and the bonding between the doctoral student and supervisor. In this context, research questions might be: What career goal should the doctorate prepare the individuals for? And what structure should a doctoral programme have in this regard?

With regard to career opportunities after the doctorate, the universities offer a lot (e.g. through their own career centres), but only some of them are attended (for individual doctorates), or they take place at a time that is not relevant for the doctoral researchers (introductory programme to PhD studies). The fact that some of the doctoral researchers interviewed took little input from the events could also be due to the fact that these offers are more general and less domain-specific. The supervisors could take a more active role here, pointing out these general offers of the university, reflecting on the event with the doctoral researchers, discussing open questions and illustrating the stronger connection to non-university career opportunities in the field of VET and beyond. This could lead to the doctoral researchers being less disoriented and being able to prepare themselves more specifically for the time after their doctorate - be it by attending relevant events or specifically looking for non-university networking opportunities.

Since all interview partners come from the VET field, the results cannot be generalised to doctoral researchers from other disciplines. In addition, the pandemic situation is an exceptional situation, and it remains to be seen to what extent this will have long-term effects and whether career patterns and desires may stay stable or change over time.

With regard to the personal effects of the pandemic, the current education report in Germany criticises the lack of support structures for socio-emotional relationships among children and adolescents (Autor:innengruppe Bildungsberichtserstattung, 2022). The results of the present study show that this is also of importance in the field of doctorates. However, there are no findings that cover the extent to which the interviewees sought and made use of support opportunities to talk about the feeling of isolation and their own depression, nor how and whether they coped with this situation and how they will deal with such situations in the future. Further research is needed on this. Additionally, it would be interesting to track the further career development of the interviewees. Can they pursue their planned career paths? What obstacles might they encounter and how could the universities provide concrete support?

The following quote will conclude this paper, demonstrating how challenging the current time is for the career development of doctoral researchers:

For me this is the huge, the biggest damage it has done for PhD-life is the networking. For two years, we have no conferences, we meet no people; we have no guest researchers. How on earth are we supposed to connect with people? And become members of a society that is out there and not only within our department. But also, within our department it is so hard like people have been recruited all these years and we did a meeting the other day, and there is fifteen new people, and you don't know anyone. So, I think the networking is like crazily damaged, and online conferences are solutions, but they cannot really compensate for the personal things. So, like this random talk with someone that just happened to sit next to you. This doesn't happen anymore. (SWE1)

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